

Identification of explosives and constituents of fuel oil in ANFO using HPTLC and GC-MS technique

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Abstract : ANFO (a mixture of NH_4NO_3 + 5-6% fuel oil), the dominant explosive used by the blasting industry can easily be smuggled from the source or can be prepared easily. Most of the blasting incidents in West Bengal were found to be due to low cost explosive ANFO (of NH_4NO_3 + 5-6% fuel oil) as evidenced from chemical analysis.

ANFO is a low cost explosive and can be triggered by any modern triggering mechanisms by the criminals. The residues collected from the crime spot and the explosives were subjected to test for ammonium ion, nitrate ion and fuel oils. However, high explosives like TNT, RDX, PETN etc. were absent.

HPTLC techniques were adopted with the new efficient solvent system Rosalac thinner and acetone mixture in the ratio (1 : 3) for the separation and identification of heavier hydrocarbons in the fuel oil as a whole. GC/MS technique was also used to confirm the presence of various constituents of fuel oil.

Keywords : ANFO, rossalac thinner, TLC, HPTLC, GC-MS.

The explosives have overwhelming contributions to different spheres of human activities like mining industry, road construction, tunneling, oil prospecting, seismographic survey, space research and also for military purposes¹. But the misuse of explosives by the criminals, antisocial and terrorists is of great concern for the common people and law enforcing authorities. Commonly used high explosives are NC (nitrocellulose), NG (nitroglycerine), TNT (trinitrotoluene), RDX (cyclonite), PETN (pentaerythritol tetranitrate). But the disastrous explosion in Texas City² in a ship loaded with fertilizer NH_4NO_3 gave birth to an inexpensive explosive ANFO i.e. ammonium nitrate and fuel oil. ANFO becomes kind of deadly bomb that shocked Oklahoma City³. At present ANFO and other ammonium nitrate based explosives account for most of the explosions occurred in India and particularly in West Bengal.

In the recent past, different districts of West Bengal witnessed several devastating explosions and in some cases, a huge amount of explosives materials were recovered. A team of forensic experts from Central Forensic Science Laboratory (CFSL, Kolkata) visited those places for helping different investigating agencies in collecting the

clue materials. They collected residues around the crime spot and also received explosive samples from investigating agencies for analytical investigations. Preliminary investigation show that the samples contained 'ANFO' or NH_4NO_3 and fuel oil. The analysis of the constituents of the explosives using simple tests TLC, HPTLC, GC-MS is the subject matter of the present investigation.

The results are reported in this paper.

Experimental

Samples : Explosive samples were regularly received by the Central Forensic Science Laboratory for the detection of explosive and identification of their constituents, other factors of investigation were mode of explosion i.e. explosion devices, place, time etc.

Samples received from different forwarding authorities were –

(a) 25 packets of explosives containing grey coloured slurry materials packed in polythene papers weighing 150 g to 450 g per packets.

(b) 3.5 kg grey coloured slurry materials.

(c) Similar explosive samples received by CFSL,

Kolkata from time to time.

(d) Residues collected from the crime spot.

Preliminary investigation like colour tests or TLC experiments showed the absence of high explosives like RDX, TNT, Tetryl, PETN *etc.* However, colour tests like Griess reagent test and Nessler's reagent tests confirmed the presence of ammonium and nitrate ions. Presence of mineral oil was also confirmed from saponification tests. The tests indicated the use of ANFO as explosives. For better comprehension, HPTLC experiments were performed with the acetone extract of the explosives using 'Rossalac' thinner and acetone mixture (1 : 3) as a solvent system. Several solvent systems [cyclohexane : chloroform (1 : 1), benzene, benzene : pet ether (1 : 1), benzene : acetone (1 : 1) *etc.*] were attempted but only 'Rossalac' thinner and acetone (1 : 3) mixture was found to be best for separation and confirmation of fuel oil. The developed spots in TLC plates were scanned by Desaga Densitometer CD 60 using UV light at 254 nm. The spots were also developed spraying 10% (w/v) of chloranil in benzene and dilute (9N) H₂SO₄ as chromogenic agent. Further confirmation of the presence of the residual hydrocarbons in the fuel oil, the hydrocarbons present in the samples were extracted with diethyl ether. GC-MS analysis of the samples were made using variable volumes of the extracts with an autosampler

with Finnigan ThermoQuest GC-MS system using the parameters – Capillary column-DB1 HT MS, oven temperature 350 °C, oven temperature was programmed between 150–350 °C with 10 °C/min increment in EI⁺ mode. Injector temperature and the interface temperature were 300 °C. The system was run at a constant flow mode using helium (1.2 ml/min) as the carrier gas.

Results and discussion

Ammonium nitrate (AN) is an easily available chemical used as a fertilizer but ANFO (ammonium nitrate with fuel oil) dominates commercial blasting industry⁴. ANFO is also most widely used explosive by the antisocials and terrorists and can easily be smuggled or purchased from the blasting personals or prepared by themselves. Different types of fuel oil were used for the preparation of explosives. Analysis of the explosive show the presence of ammonium and nitrate ions alongwith mineral oils indicating that all the explosive were ANFO. The presence of fuel oil was confirmed from HPTLC and GC-MS experiments. At 340 nm, fuel oil gave specific fluorescence in HPTLC scanner system which agreed with R_f value of diesel oil No. 5 (supplied by Indian Oil Corporation) as control (R_f 0.93). GC-MS chromatograms also show similarities with exhibit fuel oil with the control *i.e.* diesel fuel oil No. 5 of IOC. From GC-MS data and TIC values

RT: 0.00 - 18.62

Fig. 1. TIC of ANFO sample.

Table 1. Constituents of fuel oil

Compds.	Molecular formula	Set 1	Set 2	Set 3	Set 4	Set 5	Set 6
		TIC in min					
Docosane	C ₂₂ H ₄₆	23.18	11.04	11.01	-		
Tricosane	C ₂₃ H ₄₈	21.63	-	11.59	-		
Pentacosane	C ₂₅ H ₅₂	24.64	10.41	-	-		
Heptacosane	C ₂₇ H ₅₆	22.42	13.76	12.14	-		
Octacosane	C ₂₈ H ₅₈	26.15	-	12.68	-		
<i>n</i> -Nonacosane	C ₂₉ H ₆₀	15.35	13.27	13.19	-		
Heptadecane	C ₁₇ H ₃₄	23.93	-	-	9.45		17.4
Tetracosane		-	12.21	-	-		
Dodecane	C ₁₂ H ₂₄	-	9.16	-	-		
Hexatriacontane	C ₃₆ H ₇₄	-	11.64	-	-		
Pentatriacontane		-	12.76	-	-		
Octadecane		-	14.34	-	-		
1-Chloro dotriacontane	C ₃₂ H ₆₆	-	-	13.69	-		
Hexadecane	C ₁₆ H ₃₄	-	-	-	7.52		12.8
Tetradecane	C ₁₄ H ₃₀	-	-	-	7.76	8.94	10.2
2,6,10,14-Tetramethyl heptadecane	C ₂₁ H ₄₄	-	-	-	8.26		14.3
Pentadecane	C ₁₅ H ₃₂	-	-	-	8.62	10.20	15.1
Nonadecane	C ₁₉ H ₄₀	-	-	-	-	9.66	19.2
2,6,10-Trimethyl dodecane	C ₁₅ H ₃₂					8.60	
5-Methylundecane						7.26	21.7
Octanamide	C ₁₈ H ₃₅ NO						
Cetene	C ₁₆ H ₃₂						
Cetal	C ₁₆ H ₃₄ O						
Squalene	C ₃₀ H ₅₀						
Heptadecyn-1-ol	C ₁₇ H ₃₂ O						
<i>n</i> -Tridec-1-ene	C ₁₃ H ₂₆						

different constituents of fuel oil were identified as tetracosane, pentacosane, heptacosane, dodecane, heptadecane, octanamide, cetene, heptadecyn-1-ol, *n*-tridec-1-ene, squalene, cetal, docosane, tricosane, octacosane, *n*-nonacosane, hexatriacontane tetradecane, 2,6,10,14-tetramethyl heptadecane, pentadecane, hexadecane, octadecane, nonadecane, 2,6,10-trimethyl dodecane, 5-methyl undecane, pentatriacontane, 1-chloro dotriacontane.

The results were further confirmed by GC-MS⁵ (TIC) (Figs. 1–5). The data obtained from analysis of different samples were grouped into six category on the basis of similar compounds/constituents detected and is presented in Table 1. Mass fractions of different compounds (Figs. 6–12) are also presented in Table 2. The fuel oil of different ANFO contained different hydrocarbons, which characterized the different fuel oils used by different blasting agencies and terrorist groups. The mass fractions

of the fragmented ions of different hydrocarbons were the same, only the *m/z* values of different molecular ions and related fragment ions differed due to change in the molecular weight of hydrocarbons. ANFO recovered or received from different parts of West Bengal contained mostly 5–6% diesel oil.

During detonation, the fuel elements get oxidized very

Table 2. *m/z* values of different hydrocarbons

Compds.	<i>m/z</i> values
Tricosane	43, 57, 71, 85, 99, 113, 127, 141, 155
Heptacosane	41, 43, 55, 57, 67, 69, 71, 83, 85, 97, 99, 113, 127
Docosane	43, 57, 71, 85, 99, 113, 127, 141, 155
Heptadecane	43, 57, 71, 85, 99, 113, 127, 141, 155, 169, 207, 281
Pentacosane	43, 57, 71, 85, 99, 113, 127, 141, 155, 169, 207, 281
Nonacosane	43, 57, 71, 85, 99, 113, 127, 141, 155, 169, 207, 281
Octacosane	43, 57, 71, 85, 99, 113, 127, 141, 155, 169, 207, 281

Fig. 2. TIC of ANFO sample.

Fig. 3. TIC of ANFO sample.

RT: 0.00 - 21.31

Fig. 4. TIC of ANFO sample

RT: 0.00 - 29.99

Fig. 5. TIC of ANFO sample.

Std ANFO#2431 RT: 21.63 AV: 1 NL: 1.63E5
T: (0,0) + c EI det=350.00 Full ms [40.00-500.00]

Fig. 6. Mass spectra of tricosane.

EX 1027#1642 RT: 13.76 AV: 1 NL: 3.18E6
T: (0,0) + c EI det=350.00 Full ms [30.00-400.00]

Fig. 7. Mass spectra of heptacosane.

fast producing energy, therefore, available oxygen for such oxidation reactions is important for the energy

production and oxygen balance. ANFO, if, completely balanced with respect to oxygen yields maximum energy.

Std ANFO#2646 RT: 23.18 AV: 1 NL: 6.82E5
 T: (0,0) + c EI det=350.00 Full ms [40.00-500.00]

Fig. 8. Mass spectra of docosane.

Std ANFO#2750 RT: 23.93 AV: 1 NL: 2.38E5
 T: (0,0) + c EI det=350.00 Full ms [40.00-500.00]

Fig. 9. Mass spectra of heptadecane.

Std ANFO#2848 RT: 24.64 AV: 1 NL: 1.03E6
T: (0,0) + c EI det=350.00 Full ms [40.00-500.00]

Fig. 10. Mass spectra of pentacosane.

Std ANFO#2947 RT: 25.35 AV: 1 NL: 8.84E5
T: (0,0) + c EI det=350.00 Full ms [40.00-500.00]

Fig. 11. Mass spectra of nonacosane.

The above equation clearly indicates that reaction (1) always takes place to get the maximum energy. If fuel or oxidizer is in excess, harmful gases like carbon monoxide and oxides of nitrogen are produced apart from loss of energy. For this reason with AN + 5-6% fuel oil generally

Std ANFO#3057 RT: 26.15 AV: 1 NL: 6.77E5
T: {0,0} + c EI det=350.00 Full ms [40.00-500.00]

Fig. 12. Mass spectra of octacosane.

used⁶⁻⁹.

The characteristics heavier hydrocarbons from different explosion sites can also give indication of common source of origin of ANFO.

No specific container is required for placing the ANFO into the target.

It can be exploded using detonator/or in combination with modern programmable electronic delay timer device.

ANFO is cheaper than TNT, RDX, PETN, NG etc. and its easy availability and easy preparation as improvised explosives has made it more popular with the blasting agencies antisocials and terrorists.

It can be assumed that ANFO used by terrorists were smuggled from the different blasting agencies using ANFO. Mass fractions of different ANFO samples suggest that the composition of ANFO are slightly different from each other. Some of these were in the form of slurry (where NH₄NO₃ was probably thickened by some polysaccharide like guar gum) or the size of the prills of NH₄NO₃ may be different. The explosives did not contain microballons (made of phenolic resin) of crushing strength though microballons were recovered in some cases.

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